

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

D7.2 VIDEOS PRODUCED VER 1

**WP7 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION,
RRI, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT**

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Version History

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0.2	04/08/2023	Draft reviewed by the Coordinator and consortium	Project partners
1.0	09/08/2023	Final draft ready for submission	Silvia Pérez, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello

Deliverable Information

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¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	3
1. Video presentation	4
1.1 Description and links	4
1.2 Design and format.....	4
1.3 Storyboard & script	5
1.4 Dissemination strategy.....	6
Conclusions.....	7

Acronyms & Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package

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Introduction

Within the framework of the WP7 dissemination and communication activities for AquaWind, the WP Leader Consulta Europa Projects & Innovation (CE), in collaboration with the partners and thanks to the external support of Help The Studio, has worked to develop the first promotional video of the project.

As set out in the Grant Agreement, three promotional videos must be produced by AquaWind to support the dissemination and communication efforts of the project:

- A first **animation video** to inform about the project objectives and vision of it.
- A **demonstration video** of the technological and operational aspects of the AquaWind solution.
- A **storytelling video** involving staff from the project and other stakeholders involved in the project activities.

The videos are to be produced in English with subtitles in the three languages of the consortium (Spanish, Portuguese, French). These videos shall be uploaded to AquaWind's YouTube and distributed across partners' channels.

In D7.2 details of the video structure, key technical characteristics, development process and workings are outlined.

The deliverable also includes visuals of the finalised product and the planned dissemination strategy to share it with external audience after the deliverable's submission.

1. Video presentation

1.1 Description and links

The first animation video has been released at M12 (see D7.2 Videos Ver 1), with the aim of presenting the overall scope of AquaWind, its objectives, main activities, and results expected from this funding experience. The video has multiple purposes: to convey AquaWind's main messages (as defined in the D7.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan), to help raise public awareness of multi-use platforms and to promote the EU support (specifically of EMFAF) to this type of initiatives.

The video is available on the AquaWind YouTube channel:

- EN: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iuBmZY2t4XM>
- ES: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vcR_NaD_KBO
- PT: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LpE6wkNh89k>
- FR: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F_FImNPJ8CE

The English version of the video is also embedded on the **homepage** of the [website](#).

1.2 Design and format

The video has been designed and developed by CE in coordination with the contracted service provider Help The Studio (cost foreseen in the Grant Agreement). The video makes use of the visual identity and branding of AquaWind. The colours, fonts and official icons of the project are respected in the scenes of the video. The visual identity of the project was created to make it attractive and user-friendly for people of all age. The animation was developed with these guidelines in mind.

As per the Grant Agreement, the videos shall be short and simple. For the first video, a duration of ca. 2 minutes has been agreed to be the best in order to include a comprehensive description of the project whereas keeping the time limited not to lose audience's attention. To facilitate the exploitation of the video in different settings (laptops, social media profiles, smartphones and tablets, conference stands/presentations and exhibition areas), project partners have chosen a hybrid solution including text, voiceover, animations, infographics, etc. Thanks to this mix different audiences in different conditions will be able to understand and enjoy the contents.

The video acknowledges the EU financing at the beginning and at the end of the animation scenes, in line with the guidelines of Art. 17 of the Grant Agreement.

1.3 Storyboard & script

The production process of the first animation video involved CE crafting the script and collaborating with partners on its development. Following pre-production, graphic elements were designed leading to the creation of an interactive and catchy video. An overview of the storyboard drafted for the video is shown in Table 1, while the script of the video is provided in Table 2.

Table 1. Overview of video’s storyboard

Animated Video Storyboard			

Table 2. Video’s script

	Text
1	AquaWind is a collaborative project co-founded by the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund. The objective is to combine offshore renewable energy production and fish farming, as a first and unique trial on the coast of Gran Canaria in the Canary Islands, Spain.
2	AquaWind relies on an existing floating wind platform named Wind to Power (W2Power). It will be integrated with customised aquaculture cage and remote feeding and monitoring systems to track fish health and welfare and prototype structural behaviour.
3	Pilot tests will be carried out to validate the W2Power performance in combination with the aquaculture operations, also ensuring close environmental and biodiversity monitoring.
4	AquaWind research activities will be crucial to establish a novel route map for regulatory and legal issues for real implementation of multi-use marine projects. Recommendations for policy makers will also be released to support the commercialisation of hybrid wind and aquaculture technologies.

5	The AquaWind solution will be designed and tested following a multi-stakeholder and circular approach to ensure social acceptance and the lowest environmental impact.
6	This inclusive process will engage at regional, national, and European levels: Research and Innovation Stakeholders, Policy Makers, Fishery Communities, and Citizens.
7	With nine partners from Spain, France, and Portugal, the AquaWind consortium brings benefits from its expertise in the sector of marine and aquaculture research, energy systems, environmental impact assessment, project management and communication.
8	The project is a unique innovative action to support the development and uptake of combined marine activities and contributes to the Atlantic Maritime Strategy and the European Green Deal for the sustainable expansion of the Blue Economy.
9	Ultimately, AquaWind will empower business and research in the Atlantic area, by laying the foundation for future multi-use projects in the same area and beyond.

1.4 Dissemination strategy

This video will be used as dissemination tools to promote AquaWind and the consortium. It will be functional for WP7 tasks and WP1 stakeholder engagement activities. First, the video has been uploaded online on the AquaWind website and YouTube channel. Upon the deliverable submission, the video will be disseminated in the second project newsletter and dedicated promotion will be ensured via project social media from September 2023. Project partners will be encouraged to re-share this information through their own networks and channels. In addition, whenever possible, the videos will be used at events and conferences (e.g., inserted in presentation or played on laptops/screens) to illustrate the key objectives, procedures, and methodology of the project. The rationale is that the visual promotion of the project activities and outputs shall create interest around AquaWind and incentive stakeholder groups to get engaged in its dissemination activities and uptake of project results. This could also facilitate the fact that external audiences might in turn promote the project among their networks, further increasing the number of engaged stakeholders.

Figure 1. Dissemination strategy for video promotion

Conclusions

D7.2 is the first of a series of three deliverables that will report on the development of three dedicated promotional videos to support WP7 dissemination & communication activities and overall stakeholder engagement also executed through WP1 tasks.

The first introductory video has been developed, and a plan for its promotion is in place and will be implemented in the next few months. The second video is expected to be released in one year time (M24), while the third one at the end of the project (M36).

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